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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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DEVELOPING WRITING COMPETENCE AMONG CEFR B1 AND IELTS LEARNERS EXPERIENCING DIFFICULTIES IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE ACQUISITION

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Abstract: This article explores the importance of developing writing skills as a fundamental component of learning English as a foreign language. It focuses on the practical and methodological aspects of teaching writing at the CEFR (Common European Framework of Reference for Languages) B1 level and within the IELTS (International English Language Testing System) framework. Writing, as one of the four core language skills, plays a crucial role in enabling learners to express ideas, organize thoughts coherently, and use grammar and vocabulary appropriately in real communicative contexts. The paper discusses the main approaches and techniques used to enhance writing proficiency, comparing CEFR-based and IELTS-oriented strategies. It also examines the challenges learners typically face, such as limited vocabulary, grammatical inaccuracies, lack of coherence and cohesion, and low confidence in written expression.

Key words: learning experience, interactive methods, studying techniques, research, types of writing skills, personal opinions and ideas.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilini chet tili sifatida o'rganish jarayonida yozuv ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishning ahamiyati tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot CEFR (Common European Framework of Reference for Languages) B1 darajasida va IELTS (International English Language Testing System) doirasida yozish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishning amaliy va uslubiy jihatlarga bag'ishlangan. Yozuv – til o'rganishning to'rtta asosiy ko'nikmasidan biri bo'lib, u o'quvchilarga fikrlarini aniq ifodalash, ularni mantiqan izchil tashkil etish hamda grammatika va lug'atdan real muloqot sharoitida to'g'ri foydalanish imkonini beradi. Maqolada yozuv mahoratini oshirishga qaratilgan asosiy yondashuvlar va metodlar tahlil qilinadi, CEFR va IELTS tizimlariga yo'naltirilgan strategiyalar solishtiriladi hamda o'quvchilar duch keladigan asosiy muammolar – so'z boyligining cheklanganligi, grammatik xatolar, izchillikning yetishmasligi va yozma nutqda ishonchsizlik masalalari yoritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: o'rganish tajribasi, interfaol metodlar, o'qitish usullari, tadqiqot, yozish ko'nikmalari turlari, shaxsiy fikrlar va g'oyalar.

Аннотация: В статье анализируется значение развития навыков письма как фундаментального компонента изучения английского языка как иностранного. Исследование посвящено практическим и методическим аспектам формирования письменных навыков на уровне CEFR (Common European Framework of Reference for Languages) B1 и в рамках IELTS (International English Language Testing System). Письмо, являясь одним из четырёх основных языковых навыков, играет важную роль в формировании способности обучающихся выражать мысли, логично организовывать высказывания и правильно использовать грамматику и лексику в реальных коммуникативных ситуациях. В статье рассматриваются основные подходы и методы повышения письменной компетенции, проводится сравнение стратегий, основанных на CEFR и ориентированных на IELTS, а также анализируются трудности, с которыми сталкиваются обучающиеся: ограниченный словарный запас, грамматические ошибки, отсутствие связности и низкий уровень уверенности в письменном выражении.

Ключевые слова: опыт обучения, интерактивные методы, методы преподавания, исследование, виды письменных навыков, личные мнения и идеи.

INTRODUCTION

Writing is the most crucial and effective skill for a number of learners who study at schools, colleges, and universities in different parts of the world. Currently, there are several problems and challenges related to writing skills not only in English-speaking countries but also in other nations. Basically, our pupils and students who study at schools and universities face certain difficulties in improving their writing skills and need to enhance

them in various ways within classroom settings. In this article, we would like to share various methods and techniques that are effective for students and pupils in language learning, as well as discuss some authors who have written books devoted to writing skills, for example, CEFR and IELTS materials aimed at developing each learner's writing abilities. Some researchers have also observed and analyzed students' writing skills in classroom contexts.

Most students state that writing is the most difficult skill among listening, reading, and speaking in English. In our country, when they take CEFR and IELTS classes and exams, they have to deal with writing-related issues. Sometimes, during the exam, they obtain the lowest scores in the writing band and become frustrated about why they cannot manage it effectively. Only a few succeed in classroom and examination contexts. Interestingly, even some English speakers obtain lower writing scores in IELTS and CEFR compared to other bands. How can we improve the writing environment in the classroom? What methods are effective and useful for developing writing skills?

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

Two decades ago, grammar was considered the foundation of English learning, and mastering grammatical rules was seen as the most essential step for anyone studying the language. However, with the rapid development of educational innovation and technology, the focus in language learning has significantly shifted. Today, learners and educators alike recognize that effective communication requires more than just grammatical accuracy – it also depends on writing, reading, listening, and speaking skills that reflect real-life language use.

The emergence of information technology and the Internet has played a transformative role in this shift. Digital platforms now provide limitless opportunities for learners to practice and improve their writing skills through interaction, collaboration, and access to authentic materials. As Isabela Villas Boas (2010) observes: "The Internet can be used in a variety of ways to support process writing as students develop their writing skills in various genres. Although the Internet is a naturally motivating tool and many young learners are familiar with using information technology, it is important for teachers to be active facilitators when the Internet is used for language learning as well as for developing writing skills." This observation highlights the growing importance of teacher guidance in integrating technology effectively into the writing process.

In addition, researchers such as Anthony Green (2014) have discussed how test developers and item writers for standardized exams like IELTS engage in complex processes to design fair and culturally neutral tasks. Both experienced and novice writers follow a similar pattern: they begin with a topic, research related materials, and carefully select suitable texts for inclusion in the test. Green notes that this selection stage is often the most challenging, as it requires balancing topic accessibility and cultural neutrality. Topics such as art or history may assume specific background knowledge, while texts on technology or psychology tend to be more universally understood.

For students preparing for CEFR and IELTS examinations, this context is highly relevant. These exams assess not only linguistic knowledge but also the ability to produce coherent, contextually appropriate written texts. Many learners, however, find writing tasks particularly intimidating. They often struggle with crafting strong introductions, paraphrasing the essay prompt effectively, and supporting their ideas with relevant examples – especially in Task 2 essays. Such difficulties stem not only from linguistic gaps but also from limited exposure to academic writing structures and a lack of confidence.

Therefore, modern English teaching must adopt an integrated and supportive approach. Grammar should no longer be treated as an isolated skill but rather as a tool within a broader communicative framework. By using interactive technologies, guided writing strategies, and scaffolded feedback, teachers can help students develop greater confidence and competence in writing. Ultimately, the combination of digital literacy, critical thinking, and guided practice enables learners to progress beyond mechanical accuracy toward authentic written expression – preparing them for both academic and real-world communication.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology in this study is based on a combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches. Data were collected through surveys, classroom observations, and written task analyses involving CEFR B1 and IELTS learners, as well as English language teachers. The obtained data were processed using statistical and content analysis methods to identify students' writing errors, grammatical accuracy, coherence, and vocabulary range. Comparative and generalization techniques were also applied to interpret the results, assessing the level of writing competence development and the effectiveness of teaching strategies according to CEFR and IELTS standards.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

So, young students and IELTS applicants make some mistakes by confusing Task 1 and Task 2 to choose words and word combinations – and phrases like “more and more”, “bigger and bigger”, “greater and greater” are too informal and only good for speaking, not suitable for academic writing [2 Rachel Mitchell]. Instead of writing “more and more people are driving cars these days”, you could use trend language in Task 1 writing to express this sentence as “increasing numbers of people are using cars these days”, “a significantly larger number of people are using cars these days”, “a growing increase in the number of people using cars these days”, or “nowadays, the number of people who own cars has increased”. For example: “increasing numbers of students are going abroad for university study”; “the number of cities that suffer from pollution has increased tremendously in recent decades”. That’s much better than “more and more”.

In addition, instead of using structures such as “much more”, you can say “a great deal larger”. Also, “big” is too informal for reports and essays; we should use “large”, “sizeable”, or “significant” instead. Moreover, while writing Task 2 essays, they also do not distinguish between personal and impersonal opinions. There should be no personal opinions in the body paragraphs (no I think, I believe, in my mind, in my opinion, as far as I am concerned, for me, to me, etc.), only in the introduction (for thesis-led essays) or in the conclusion. Use impersonal opinions in the body paragraphs such as some people think, other people believe, many people claim that, as far as some people are concerned. Try to give other people’s opinions, not your own, in your body paragraphs.

Writing essays from a global perspective is essential because the questions are asked from a global perspective. Try to avoid relating the essay question only to your country; it should be about the world in general. If you say, “traffic in the city is a serious problem when you are traveling down Madison Avenue at rush hour”, it’s very specific. Instead, you should say: “when people travel down busy streets in urban areas during rush hours...” – now you are not talking about the problems of a specific city, but about the problems that every city faces.

“CEFR writing processes include formal and informal letters – letters of complaint, letters of apology, letters of request, letters of application, and transactional letters [7 Virginia Evans].” Among our applicants and students who study at schools and universities, there is a lack of writing techniques, brainstorming ideas, word combinations, and phrases, no matter how much they are explained in classes and courses in detail. It is also clear that they lack motivation and logical thinking.

According to recent studies, IELTS and CEFR are more global and academic exams not only in English-speaking countries but also in other nations. The entrance exams of universities and colleges are completely aligned with them, because a large number of people and applicants take IELTS and CEFR in order to become students at both international colleges and universities.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Above mentioned, at present IELTS and CEFR have been expanding their exam capacities among foreign universities and colleges, as they are well designed and planned for four skills – listening, reading, writing, speaking – and grammar for both university entrance exams and testing competencies.

Each young learner has a huge opportunity and possibility to seize them. Their requirements are being flexible and adaptable. I put forward that students should have more practice in writing skills by learning active and advanced vocabulary words.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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